

The Current Situation of Barriers to Pain Self-Management Among Cancer Patients Treated at the Oncology – Nuclear Medicine Center, Vinh Phuc General Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To describe the current situation of barriers to pain self-management among cancer patients treated at the Oncology – Nuclear Medicine Center, Vinh Phuc General Hospital.

Materials and methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted on 116 cancer patients from January to June 2023. Data were collected using BQ-II, PSEQ, MMAS-8, PHQ-2, ECOG/WHO PS, and BPI-sfvn. SPSS 22.0 was applied for data analysis.

Results: The mean score of cognitive barriers was 2.22 ± 0.48 (moderate level), with the greatest concerns being drug tolerance (3.30 ± 0.97) and immune suppression (2.89 ± 1.26). Pain self-efficacy was low ($24.97 \pm 10.91/60$). The mean medication adherence score was $7.29 \pm 1.91/11$, with 50% showing high adherence and 25% low adherence. About 35.3% of patients had suspected major depressive disorder, 43.1% had poor performance status, and the average pain level was moderate (3.64 ± 1.50), with the worst pain remaining high (5.14 ± 1.66).

Conclusions: Cancer patients still face multiple barriers to pain self-management, including concerns about analgesics, low self-efficacy, uneven adherence, depression, and poor performance status. Nurses play a crucial role in patient education, psychological support, and monitoring treatment adherence, in conjunction with multidisciplinary care, to enhance pain control and improve quality of life.

KEYWORDS: Barriers, pain self-management, medication adherence, cancer patients, nursing.

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INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a leading cause of death worldwide. According to GLOBOCAN 2020, approximately 19.3 million new cancer cases and nearly 10 million cancer-related deaths are recorded annually [1]. In Vietnam, there are an estimated 182,563 new cases and 122,690 deaths annually, making cancer a major public health and social burden [2]. In addition to disease-specific treatment, symptom management, particularly pain control, plays a crucial role in improving the quality of life of patients.

Pain is one of the most common and distressing symptoms experienced by patients with cancer. Numerous studies have indicated that 30–50% of patients in the early stages and 70–90% of those with advanced cancer suffer from pain [3]. Persistent pain not only affects physical functioning but also negatively impacts psychological well-being, sleep quality, social relationships, and treatment adherence,

thereby substantially reducing the overall quality of life [4]. Consequently, effective pain management is a core objective of palliative care and oncology nursing [5].

However, evidence from studies worldwide and in Vietnam suggests that inadequate pain control remains prevalent, with approximately 30–50% of patients failing to achieve satisfactory pain relief [6]. One of the main reasons is the presence of barriers to pain self-management, including cognitive barriers, such as patients' concerns about analgesics, especially opioids, due to fears of addiction or adverse effects [7]; barriers related to self-efficacy, resulting from a lack of confidence in one's ability to control pain [8]; physical condition-related barriers, where fatigue, poor appetite, and physical deterioration reduce patients' ability to participate in treatment [9]; psychological barriers, such as anxiety and depression, which hinder adherence to treatment regimens [10]; and medication adherence barriers, including

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missed doses, self-discontinuation of analgesics, or fear of side effects [11]. In addition, pain intensity itself constitutes a significant barrier to self-management, as severe pain may cause patients to abandon control strategies or feel discouraged by the perceived ineffectiveness of analgesics [12].

In Vietnam, despite significant advances in cancer diagnosis and treatment, barriers to pain self-management persist and substantially affect care effectiveness. Several studies have shown that patients continue to have limitations in knowledge, attitudes, and skills related to pain self-control, leading to suboptimal treatment outcomes [2], [9].

Vinh Phuc General Hospital is the primary cancer treatment center in the region, admitting a large number of patients with oncology conditions annually. However, to date, few studies have focused on clarifying the current status of barriers to pain self-management at this hospital. Assessing and identifying these barriers will provide important scientific and practical evidence to inform the development of appropriate intervention strategies, enhance pain control effectiveness, and improve the quality of life of cancer patients in the local context. Therefore, this study was conducted to provide scientific evidence to support more effective care and patient-support strategies.

METHODS

Participants

Cancer patients receiving treatment at Vinh Phuc Provincial General Hospital.

Selection criteria:

- Aged ≥ 18 years;
- Diagnosed with cancer and experiencing pain;
- No cognitive impairment;
- Able to hear, speak, read, and write Vietnamese.

Exclusion criteria:

- Poor performance status (ECOG/WHO) at stage 4;
- Pain caused by other concomitant chronic diseases such as gout or arthritis;
- Patients with cancer who had undergone surgery within ≤ 1 month;
- Failure to fully participate in health education interventions or all assessment sessions during the study period.

Time and place of study

The study was conducted from January 2023 to June 2023 at Vinh Phuc Provincial General Hospital.

Study design: A cross-sectional descriptive study design was used.

Sampling method

A total population sampling method was used, including all patients with cancer who met the inclusion criteria during the study period. A total of 116 patients were recruited for this study.

Data collection tools and methods

Data collection instruments: General patient information: A structured questionnaire consisting of 16 items divided into two sections: self-reported patient information (items A1–A11) and data extracted from medical records (items A12–A16). Instruments measuring barriers to pain self-management: Barriers Questionnaire II (BQ-II) for cognitive barriers to pain management, Pain Self-Efficacy Questionnaire (PSEQ), the eight-item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8) for adherence to analgesic therapy; Patient Health Questionnaire-2 (PHQ-2) for mental health assessment; ECOG/WHO Performance Status, Brief Pain Inventory – short form, Vietnamese version (BPI-sfvn).

Data collection method: Data were collected through face-to-face interviews with patients and review of medical records.

Assessment standards

Cognitive barriers: Cognitive barriers include eight common aspects, such as fear of addiction, fear of tolerance to analgesics, concerns about side effects, beliefs that increasing pain indicates disease progression, and perceptions that pain is uncontrollable. The mean score (MS) for each barrier was calculated from its component items; the overall mean score was calculated as the average of all 27 items. Higher mean scores indicated greater levels of perceived barriers.

Pain self-management self-efficacy: The Vietnamese version of the PSEQ consists of 10 items, each rated on a 7-point Likert scale (0 = not at all confident to 6 = completely confident). Higher scores indicate greater confidence in pain coping.

Mental health status: The PHQ-2 comprises two items assessing the frequency of depressive mood symptoms. Each item is rated on a 4-point Likert scale (0 = not at all to 3 = nearly every day). A PHQ-2 score ≥ 3 suggests a high likelihood of major depressive disorder.

Adherence to analgesic medication: The MMAS-8 includes eight items. Items 1–7 are answered “Yes/No”: for items 1–4 and 6–7, “Yes” = 0 and “No” = 1; for item 5, “Yes” = 1 and “No” = 0. Item 8 is rated on a 5-point Likert scale (0–4). The total scores range from 0 to 11 and are classified as good adherence (8–11), moderate adherence (6–7), and low adherence (0–5).

Performance status: The ECOG/WHO Performance Status scale includes five levels, ranging from 0 (fully active, able to carry on all pre-disease activities without restriction) to 4 (completely disabled; unable to carry out any self-care; totally confined to bed or chair). The performance status was categorized as good (0–1) or poor (2–4).

Pain intensity: Pain intensity for each pain condition was classified as: no pain (0), mild pain (1–3), moderate pain (4–6), and severe pain (7–10) [15]. The mean pain score was calculated as the total score of all pain conditions divided by four. Overall pain severity was classified based on the mean pain score as mild [1,4), moderate [4,7), or severe [7,10].

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Data analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 22.0. Statistical significance was set at $p = 0.05$. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize frequencies, percentages, and mean values of study variables.

Ethical considerations: The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Nam Dinh University of Nursing. All patient information was kept confidential and used only for research purposes.

RESULTS

Characteristics of Participants

Out of the total 116 patients with cancer who participated in the study, 77.6% male, 22.4% female, 65.5% were elderly

cancer patients, 96.6% Kinh ethnicity, 94% general education, married 87.1%, rural/mountainous/midland 94.8%; lung 33.8%, liver 12.1%, stomach 13.8%, colorectal 6.9%, and breast 6.0%; late stage 78.5%; therapy: Chemotherapy and radiation therapy 11.2%, chemotherapy/targeted 28.4%, palliative care 50%, other 10.4%; Analgesic used at level 2 (66.4%), level 1 (29.3%), level 3 (4.3%); good performance status 56.9%. Health Insurance 99.1%; main carer is father/mother/spouse/child 93.1%; agriculture 62.1%, workers 8.6%, service/trade 6%, other 23.3%; poor households 15.5%, and average/good 84.5%.

Current Status of Barriers to Pain Self-Management Among Patients

Table 1. Cognitive barriers to pain self-management among cancer patients (n=116).

Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Mean \pm SD
Overall barriers	0.85	3.22	2.22 \pm 0.48
Side effects	0	5.00	2.11 \pm 0.95
Drug tolerance	0	4.67	3.30 \pm 0.97
Symptom masking	0	4.67	2.36 \pm 1.18
Beliefs in medication and pain relief	0	4.00	1.56 \pm 0.77
Desire to be a good patient	0.67	4.00	1.98 \pm 0.62
Fear of distracting physicians	0	4.67	1.34 \pm 0.94
Fear of addiction	0	4.67	2.31 \pm 1.21
Immune system dysfunction	0	4.00	2.89 \pm 1.26
Pain self-management efficacy	5	49	24.97 \pm 10.91

Table 1 shows that cognitive barriers to pain self-management among cancer patients were moderate (mean 2.22 ± 0.48). The most common barriers were concerns about drug tolerance and immune effects, followed by fear of

addiction and side effects. In contrast, the least significant barriers were fear of distracting physicians and lack of trust in pain medication. Pain self-management efficacy was low ($24.97 \pm 10.91/60$).

Table 2. Adherence to analgesic medication among patients with cancer (n=116).

Adherence level	Frequency (%)	Mean \pm SD
High	58 (50.0)	8.91 \pm 0.84
Moderate	29 (25.0)	6.66 \pm 0.48
Low	29 (25.0)	4.69 \pm 0.60
Overall mean		7.29 \pm 1.91

Table 2 indicates that adherence to analgesic medication among cancer patients was relatively positive, with 50% demonstrating high adherence. However, 25% of

patients showed moderate adherence, and another 25% low adherence. The overall mean adherence score was 7.29 ± 1.91 out of 11, reflecting a moderately good level of adherence.

Table 3. Mental health status among patients with cancer (n=116).

Mental health status	Frequency (%)	Mean \pm SD
Indicative of major depressive disorder	41 (35.3)	3.41 \pm 0.55
Not indicative of major depressive disorder	75 (64.7)	1.24 \pm 0.80
Overall mean		2.01 \pm 1.29

Table 3 shows that 35.3% of cancer patients were suggestive of major depressive disorder. The mean PHQ-2

score is 2.01 ± 1.29 , indicating concerning mental health status.

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Table 4. Physical condition of patients with cancer (n=116).

Physical condition	Frequency (%)	Mean ± SD
Good (0–1)	66 (56.9)	0.95 ± 0.21
Poor (2–4)	50 (43.1)	2.20 ± 0.40
Overall mean		1.41 ± 0.69

Table 4 shows that 56.9% of patients had good physical status, while 43.1% were in poor condition, with an overall mean score of 1.41 ± 0.69. This indicates that nearly

half of the patients with cancer experience physical limitations.

Figure 1. Classification of general pain in patients with cancer (n=116)

Figure 1 shows that the majority of patients with cancer experienced mild (56.90%) or moderate (37.90 %) pain, while severe pain accounted for only 5.20%. However,

a considerable proportion of patients still reported moderate-to-severe pain, indicating the need for timely attention and appropriate interventions to improve their quality of life.

Table 5. Classification of Pain Intensity and Mean Pain Scores in Cancer Patients (n=116)

Pain intensity	Mild n (%)	Moderate n (%)	Severe n (%)	Mean ± SD
Worst pain	30 (25.9)	69 (59.4)	17 (14.7)	5.14 ± 1.66
Least pain	98 (84.5)	15 (12.9)	3 (2.6)	2.36 ± 1.39
Average pain	46 (39.7)	64 (55.2)	4 (5.2)	3.70 ± 1.49
Current pain	68 (58.6)	39 (33.6)	9 (7.8)	3.37 ± 2.00
Overall mean				3.64 ± 1.50

Table 5 shows that the overall mean pain score among patients with cancer was 3.64 ± 1.50, indicating a moderate level of pain. Specifically, the highest mean score was observed for worst pain (5.14 ± 1.66), indicating that many patients still experience severe pain episodes. In contrast, the lowest mean score was recorded for least pain (2.36 ± 1.39), suggesting that pain can be alleviated but not completely relieved. The mean scores for average pain (3.70 ± 1.49) and current pain (3.37 ± 2.00) indicate that pain remains a persistent issue among patients with cancer.

± 0.48, indicating a moderate level. The most prominent barriers were concerns about drug tolerance (3.30 ± 0.97) and immune system effects (2.89 ± 1.26), followed by fear of drug addiction (2.31 ± 1.21) and concerns about the side effects (2.11 ± 0.95). In contrast, less common barriers included fear of distracting physicians and distrust of analgesic medications.

These findings reflect the common psychological concerns among cancer patients when using opioids and analgesic drugs. Patients often worry about the risk of addiction, side effects, and long-term impacts on health, thereby limiting their cooperation and reducing the effectiveness of pain control. Ward et al. (1993), when developing the BQ-II scale, also indicated that fear of addiction and drug tolerance were the most common barriers among cancer patients using opioids [13].

DISCUSSION

Cognitive barriers among cancer patients:

Regarding cognitive barriers among cancer patients, the mean score of cognitive barriers in pain self-management was 2.22

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Similarly, a systematic review by Oldenmenger et al. (2009) showed that more than 60% of cancer patients were still reluctant to use strong analgesics because of concerns about side effects and drug dependence [14]. In Vietnam, Nguyen Thi Thu Ha et al. (2020) reported that patients still had many misconceptions about analgesic medications, particularly those related to addiction and side effects [15]. These results have practical implications, indicating that nurses must play a key role in explaining, counseling, and supporting patients in overcoming cognitive barriers. Providing scientific information, health education communication, and psychological support helps patients correctly understand analgesic medications, especially opioids, thereby enhancing treatment cooperation, improving pain self-management effectiveness, and improving the quality of life of patients with cancer.

The mean pain self-efficacy score (PSEQ) among cancer patients was only 24.97 ± 10.91 out of 60 points, reflecting a low level of confidence in pain control and coping strategies. This indicates that most patients were not truly proactive in applying pain control measures and still depended heavily on healthcare professionals and analgesics. This result reflects the reality that patients with cancer are often affected by anxiety, fatigue, and lack of knowledge about pain management, which reduces their confidence in their ability to control pain. Compared with the study by Nicholas (1989), patients with a mean PSEQ score higher than 30 points were considered to have relatively good self-efficacy, whereas the mean score in this study was below this threshold [16]. Similarly, Ferreira-Valente et al. (2011) showed that PSEQ levels were closely related to coping ability and quality of life in patients with chronic pain, in which the group with low PSEQ scores often experienced more difficulties in pain management [17]. In Vietnam, several recent studies have reported that patients with cancer have low pain self-management self-efficacy, mainly due to the lack of appropriate health education programs and psychological support [18]. These findings have implications for self-care practices, indicating that nurses need to implement counseling programs, pain coping skills training, and enhanced psychological support to improve patients' confidence and initiative in pain control. Improving pain self-efficacy not only helps patients reduce their dependence on medications but also improves their quality of life, reduces psychological stress, and enhances adaptability during the treatment process.

Adherence to analgesic medication: Regarding adherence to analgesic medication, the mean adherence score among cancer patients was 7.29 ± 1.91 out of 11 points, indicating a moderate-to-good level. Of these, 50% of the patients had high adherence, 25% had moderate adherence, and 25% had low adherence. This reflects an inconsistency in the use of analgesic medications as prescribed, mainly due to

missed doses, self-discontinuation of medication, or concerns about side effects and fear of opioid dependence. This result is consistent with the study by Morisky et al. (2008), which showed that medication adherence often fluctuates and rarely reaches optimal levels [19], as well as the study by Wang et al. (2018), which reported that only approximately 55% of cancer patients fully adhered to opioid use [20]. In practice, adherence to analgesic medication plays a decisive role in symptom control but remains a challenge among cancer patients. Therefore, nurses should focus on health education, individualized counseling, guidance on correct dosage and timing, clear explanation of benefits and side effects, and coordination with family members to support patients. These solutions will help improve adherence, thereby enhancing pain control effectiveness and quality of life among patients with cancer.

Mental health status: Regarding mental health, 35.3% of patients with cancer were suggested to have major depressive disorder, with a mean PHQ-2 score of 2.01 ± 1.29 , indicating that mental health remains problematic. This proportion is consistent with the study by Mitchell et al. (2011) [21], which showed that depression is common among patients with cancer. Poor mental health may increase cognitive barriers to pain management and reduce adherence to analgesic medication, as patients are more likely to feel anxious and pessimistic, forget doses, or discontinue medication on their own. This suggests that mental healthcare should be integrated in parallel with pain control in cancer treatment. Early screening and detection of depression and anxiety disorders, combined with counseling and psychological support programs, will help patients improve their confidence and better cooperate with treatment. The role of nurses in this process is particularly important, as they provide both physical care and emotional support, thereby improving the overall quality of life of cancer patients.

Performance status: Regarding patient performance status, 56.9% of cancer patients had good performance status, while 43.1% had poor performance status, with a mean score of 1.41 ± 0.69 . This indicates that nearly half of the patients had a reduced performance status, which affected their self-care ability and treatment cooperation. This result is consistent with the study by Buccheri et al. (1996) [22], which showed that poor performance status is associated with a worse prognosis and reduced pain control effectiveness. In clinical practice, patients with cancer and poor performance status often experience fatigue, loss of appetite, and limited mobility, thereby reducing medication adherence and increasing the burden of barriers in pain management. This emphasizes the role of nurses in regularly assessing performance status, providing nutritional counseling, encouraging appropriate physical activity, and coordinating multidisciplinary care for

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patients. Timely interventions not only help improve performance status but also enhance pain control effectiveness and quality of life in patients with cancer.

Pain intensity: Mild pain accounted for 56.9% of the cases, moderate pain for 37.9%, and severe pain for only 5.2%. This indicates that pain control was generally at an acceptable level; however, nearly 40% of patients still experienced moderate-to-severe pain, which significantly affected their quality of life. This result is consistent with the review by van den Beuken-van Everdingen et al. (2007), who reported that 30–40% of cancer patients still suffer from moderate to severe pain despite treatment [3]. In Vietnam, Nguyen Thi Mai (2020) [23] reported that more than one-third of cancer patients experienced moderate or higher levels of pain, similar to the findings of this study. Although pain was controlled in most patients, those with moderate-to-severe pain required special attention. Nurses play an important role in regularly monitoring pain intensity, evaluating treatment effectiveness, early detection of cases of suboptimal pain control, and coordinating with physicians to adjust medications and apply supportive pain relief measures. This approach will help reduce persistent pain and improve the quality of life of patients with cancer.

The overall mean pain score among patients with cancer was 3.64 ± 1.50 , indicating a moderate level of pain. Among these, worst pain (5.14 ± 1.66) remained high, indicating that many patients experienced severe pain episodes, whereas current pain (3.37 ± 2.00) and average pain (3.70 ± 1.49) reflected persistent pain conditions. These results are consistent with those of van den Beuken-van Everdingen (2007) and Nguyen Thi Mai (2020), both of whom reported a considerable proportion of cancer patients with moderate to severe pain. This highlights the role of nurses in regular pain assessment, monitoring both worst and current pain, and combining medication adjustment with supportive measures to enhance the effectiveness of pain control.

CONCLUSIONS

Cancer patients still face many barriers in pain self-management, particularly concerns about drug tolerance, addiction, and side effects, while pain self-management self-efficacy remains low. Adherence to analgesic medication was moderate-to-good, but a significant proportion of patients still demonstrated suboptimal adherence. In addition, depression, poor performance status, and moderate-to-severe pain remain common, affecting pain control and quality of life. The study findings emphasize the necessity of integrating pain management with mental health care and improving performance status, rather than focusing solely on pharmacological treatment. Nurses play a key role in this process through counseling, health education, psychological

support, adherence monitoring, and multidisciplinary collaborations. Comprehensive and individualized interventions will help reduce barriers, enhance pain control effectiveness, and improve the quality of life of cancer patients.

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